

1 **Comparison of the transcriptional properties of low- and high-risk HPV E5.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 The human papillomavirus contains just 8 genes (the early genes E1, E2, E4, E5, E6 and E7 and
8 the late genes L1 and L2) and is capable of subverting the function of 22,000 human genes and causing
9 millions of deaths. While the functions of E6 and E7 - targeting and degradation of the p53 and Rb1 tumor
10 suppressors - are well understood, the function of E5 is less well understood. We used whole
11 transcriptome technologies to discover functions of E5 in an unbiased fashion. Both low and high risk
12 HPVE5 were capable of modulating EGFR signaling to some extent. Interestingly, modulation of
13 interferon signaling was specific to high-risk HPVE5. We recently described expression of interferon
14 pathway genes as a central aspect of senescence. These methods enabled us to differentiate for the first
15 time discrete functions of high and low risk HPV E5.
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28